

**Süni intellekt: nəzəriyyədən prktikaya, beynəlxalq konfrans,
17-18 sentyabr 2024, Naxçıvan Azərbaycan**

**FEDERATIV ÖYRƏNMƏDƏ MÜXTƏLİF BİRLƏŞDİRMƏ
YANAŞMALARININ MÜQAYİSƏLİ ANALİZİ
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT APPROACHES FOR
AGGREGATION STEP IN FEDERATED LEARNING**

Samir ƏLİYEV¹

aliyev.samir@asoiu.edu.az

ORCID ID: 0009-0006-9793-0125

Fidan NƏBİYEVƏ

fidan.nabiyeva2003@gmail.com

Əli DADAŞOV

alidadaszada6@gmail.com

¹*Azərbaycan Dövlət Neft və Sənaye Universiteti*

XÜLASƏ

Federativ öyrənmə (FL) çoxsaylı müştərilərin öz şəxsi məlumatlarını paylaşmadan global modelin birgə təlimini təmin edən paylanmış maşın öyrənməsi yanaşmasıdır və beləliklə verilənlərin məxfiliyinin qorunmasını təmin edir. FedPER alqoritmi, klientlətə onların lokal öyrətmə nümunələrinə əsasən çəki təyin edən və müxtəlif data paylanmaları üzrə modelin performansını yaxşılaşdırmağı hədəfləyən fərdiləşdirilmiş federativ öyrənmə metodudur. Lakin, müştərinin əhəmiyyətini yalnız öyrətmə nümunələrinin sayına əsasən müəyyən etmək hər bir müştərinin global modelə müxtəlif töhfələrini tam əks etdirməyə bilər. Bu məqalə daha effektiv çəki təyin etmələri üçün FedPER alqoritminin qeyri-səlis məntiqi sistemləri və analitik iyerarxiya prosesi ilə təkmilləşdirilməsini təklif edir. Müştərinin əhəmiyyəti siniflərin paylanması, təlim ölçüsü və hər bir müştərinin hesablama gücü kimi amillərə əsaslanaraq qiymətləndirildi. Bu metodların şəkillərin sinifləndirilməsində səmərəliliyini yoxlamaq üçün CIFAR-10 və FMNIST məlumat dəstlərində sınaqdan keçirildi. Proses zamanı bu yanaşmaların məhdudiyətləri və üstünlükləri araşdırıldı. Nəticələr hər bir müştəri üçün yerli modelin dəqiqliyində kiçik bir irəliləyiş göstərdi. Bununla belə, nəticələr fərqli hiperparametrlər və quruluşlardan istifadə etməklə dəqiqliyin daha da artırılması üçün hələ də imkanların olduğunu göstərir.

Реферат

Федеративное обучение (FL) — это распределенный подход к машинному обучению, который позволяет нескольким клиентам совместно обучать глобальную модель, не делясь своими локальными данными, тем самым сохраняя конфиденциальность. Алгоритм FedPER — это персонализированный метод федеративного обучения, который назначает веса клиентам на основе их локальных обучающих выборок, стремясь улучшить производительность модели в различных распределениях данных. Однако, полагаясь исключительно на количество обучающих выборок для определения важности клиента, можно не полностью охватить различные вклады каждого клиента в глобальную модель. В этой статье предлагается усовершенствовать алгоритм FedPER путем включения систем нечеткого вывода (FIS) и процесса аналитической иерархии

**2024 International Conference on Artificial intelligence: from theory to practice,
17-18 september 2024, Nakhchivan, Azerbaijan**

(АНР) для более сложных назначений весов. Важность клиента оценивалась на основе таких факторов, как распределение классов, размер обучения и вычислительная мощность каждого клиента. Эти методы были протестированы на наборах данных CIFAR-10 и FMNIST для проверки эффективности этих алгоритмов в задачах классификации изображений. В ходе процесса были исследованы ограничения и преимущества этих подходов. Результаты показали небольшое улучшение точности локальной модели для каждого клиента. Однако результаты показали, что еще есть возможности для дальнейшего повышения точности с использованием различных гиперпараметров и настроек.

ABSTRACT

Federated learning (FL) is a distributed machine learning approach that enables multiple clients to collaboratively train a global model without sharing their local data, thus preserving privacy. The FedPER algorithm is a personalized federated learning method that assigns weights to clients based on their local training samples, aiming to improve model performance across diverse data distributions. However, relying solely on the number of training samples to determine client importance may not fully capture the varying contributions of each client to the global model. This paper proposes enhancing the FedPER algorithm by incorporating fuzzy inference systems (FIS) and the analytic hierarchy process (AHP) for more sophisticated weight assignments. Client importance was graded based on factors such as the distribution of the classes, training size, and computational power of each client. These methods were tested on CIFAR-10 and FMNIST datasets to test the efficiency of these algorithms on image classification tasks. During the process, the limitations and advantages of these approaches were investigated. Results showed a slight improvement in the local model's accuracy for each client. However, the results indicated that there is still room for further increases in accuracy using different hyperparameters and settings.

Keywords: Federated Personalization, Fuzzy Inference System, Analytical Hierarchical Process, Client Selection

I. Introduction

Federated Learning (FL) is a new branch of Machine Learning focusing on concepts such as distributed computing, data privacy and Internet of Things (IoT) (Kairouz, 2019). Unlike traditional ML where server collects all data from clients to initialize training process, in Federated Learning clients train their model locally without concerning about their data privacy. Locally trained models are aggregated at the server and new global model is used by clients. However, FL comes with challenges, Non-IID (Non Independent and Identically Distributed) data is one of the most difficult challenges FL encounters. Different distributions cause variance on the parameters of local models which makes global model unstable. Also, clients with highly imbalanced data may cause global model to be more focused on this majority class. Another challenge of FL is choosing aggregation algorithm. After local models are sent to server, the parameters are aggregated with some predefined aggregation algorithm. FedAVG, SCAFFOLD, FedPER, FedMixAVG are to name few of these algorithms (Qi, P., Chiaro, 2023). These algorithms and their modifications have been tested in different research works. However, there are still some problems are waiting for their solution. FedPER algorithm divides neural network into two parts: Base layers and Personalization layers. In neural networks, early layers are usually extract more basic

AICON
2024

**Süni intellekt: nəzəriyyədən prktikaya, beynəlxalq konfrans,
17-18 sentyabr 2024, Naxçıvan Azərbaycan**

features. The idea behind FedPER is that latter layers which are used to extract more detailed features are not aggregated since they are client specific. But base layers are aggregated at server in the same FedAVG which aggregated all the layers. The problem with FedAVG is its simplicity. It takes weighted average of all parameters and these weights are assigned based on training samples they used for training their local models ignoring other attributes of clients which can make impact on the performance of the model. In literature, there have been some works to improve the performance of FedAVG using different approaches.

The goal of this work is to answer the following question: Is applying soft computing approaches will improve the performance of FedPER same way as it did in FedAVG (Aliyev, 2022 and Aliyev, 2023). In this work we tried to modify FedPER algorithm in which clients get weights using soft computing approaches such as Fuzzy Inference System and Analytical Hierarchical Process.

There have been several works done to optimize the performance of Federated Learning. Federated Learning with Personalization Layers (FedPER) is proposed by Manoj Ghuhana Arivazhagan et al. (Arivazhagan, 2019). Authors implemented a model where the model consists of base and personalized layers. Base layers share common weights for all client where personalized layers are kept individually to adapt individual data. Usually, personalized layers are last ones since last layers play more decisive roles in decision making. Base layers are aggregated by Federated Averaging (FedAVG) algorithm. Note that, when the personalized layers are absent, this algorithm becomes FedAVG algorithm. Experiments show that the FedPER algorithm outperformed FedAVG. The downside of this work was it used FedAVG algorithm to aggregate the base layers. Although FedAVG is one of the famous aggregation algorithms, it only takes the number of training samples of each client during aggregation process. Deng Yuyang et al. developed Adaptive Personalized Federated Learning (APFL) to overcome the limitation of local models to personalize (Yuyang, 2020). This method local models are trained by clients and supporting the global model. The main difference of this approach from FedPER is that non-selected clients in the communication round keep their previous local model while others send their local model to be aggregated to server. The choosing optimal step length and mixing parameters is also addressed in this work.

Federated Learning has been applied in the field of image classification too. One of such works is done by using Active Learning (AL) (Ahmed L., 2020). Dataset used in this work was images from natural disasters and water classification. Features was extracted by ResNET and then authors applied AL for training local models. Trained models were aggregated in the server by FedAVG algorithm. The results of this work confirmed that AL models can be equally beneficial in the context of Federated Learning. In another work (Chen H.Y., 2021), authors suggested the Federated Robust Decoupling (Fed-RoD) algorithm. The goal of this paper was to find bridging between generic FL in which global model is evaluated, and personalized FL where local models are evaluated. They introduced Balanced Risk Minimization (BRM) to generic FL to improve the performance. Method was tested on CIFAR-10/100 and FMNIST dataset. It can be implied from the observations outperformed other generic and personalized FL methods.

As mentioned above, one of the downsides of FedAVG is clients are given weights based on the training samples they used. One of the suggested solutions is applying Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) to client selection (Aliyev, 2023). Authors used three attributes – dataset size, distribution of classes and computational power for weighting clients. Obtained weights are used to evaluate and compare the results

2024 International Conference on Artificial intelligence: from theory to practice, 17-18 september 2024, Nakhchivan, Azerbaijan

of both original FedAVG and new approach. Authors considered balancing of the dataset as the most important factor, followed by dataset size and computation power. From the results it can be observed that using AHP for client selection produced better results. Same set of attributes were applied to Fuzzy Inference System in another work (Aliyev, 2022). Mamdani-type FIS with three input and one output variable was used. In that research work, it was concluded that applying FIS for weighting clients outperformed both original and AHP methods. However, these methods were applied to FedAVG where main learning methods is Logistic Regression. These methods can be extended and tested with neural network architectures. Another problem with FIS is the lack of experts in that area.

In this work we tried to apply FedPER algorithm to FMNIST and CIFAR-10 dataset. But taking into consideration the downsides of only using size of training data for aggregation, we applied AHP and FIS. The paper consist of 3 sections. In the second sections, current related works in the area are explored and short review about them is given. Third section is dedicated to main methods have been applied in order to achieve the goal of the paper. Fourth section represents the obtained results. In last section, conclusion and potential future works are discussed.

II. Methodology

In this paper, we focus on the estimation of weights for the clients using both AHP and FIS, based on client data and computational characteristics. Despite the popularity of the FedAvg method, we enhance it by incorporating additional factors such as class balance and computational power, making the weighting system more robust and adaptive to client variations.

Analytic Hierarchy Process

The AHP is a multi-criteria decision-making approach that provides a systematic method to prioritize and evaluate complex decisions. Developed by Thomas Saaty, AHP uses both quantitative and qualitative data to generate a ranking of alternatives by comparing them across a set of criteria (Saaty, 1987). It is particularly useful when decisions involve trade-offs between multiple factors. In the context of federated learning, AHP is used to assign optimal weights to clients based on several important attributes such as data size, class balance, and computational power.

The first step is constructing the pairwise comparison matrix where the relative importance of the three attributes (data size, class balance, and computational power) is compared. Each entry is given value between 1 and 9 where 1 means equal importance, 9 stands for absolute importance and the higher the intermediate values are, the more important that attribute over another is. The matrix is reciprocal, meaning if one attribute is rated higher, the inverse rating is given for the other. Table 1 shows the preference matrix used in this work.

	Size	Balance	Power
Size	1	1/3	7
Balance	3	1	9
Power	1/7	1/9	1

Table 1 Preference Matrix

**Süni intellekt: nəzəriyyədən prktikaya, beynəlxalq konfrans,
17-18 sentyabr 2024, Naxçıvan Azərbaycan**

Prioritization process was done Geometric Mean. Consistency checking is one of the most important steps in AHP. Consistency ratio for the given matrix was calculated and got value 0.068. Value is less than 0.1, which implies that matrix can be used for AHP.

Fuzzy Inference System

FIS is multilevel decision-making system. The Mamdani-type FIS is applied to compute client weights using fuzzy logic, a method that mimics human decision-making by evaluating vague and uncertain information (Chai Y., 2009). Three attributes mentioned in previous section were given to FIS as input and client weights were returned as output. All attributes were partitioned into 3 variables:

Size : Small, Medium, Large

Balance: Highly imbalanced, Imbalanced and Balanced

Power: Weak , Medium, Strong

Membership functions are given in figure 1.

Following set of rules were applied:

1. If Size=Small and Balance=Highly imbalanced then weight=Weak
2. If Size=Large and Balance=Balanced then weight=Strong
3. If Size=Small and Balance=Balanced then weight=Mid
4. If Size=Mid then weight=Mid
5. If Size=Large and Balance=Highly balanced then weight=Mid
6. If Cpower=Bad then weight=Weak
7. If Cpower=Mid then weight=Mid
8. If Cpower=Good then weight=Strong

Centroid of Area (CoA) was used as defuzzification method in this work.

III. Experiments and Results

2024 International Conference on Artificial intelligence: from theory to practice, 17-18 september 2024, Nakhchivan, Azerbaijan

Experiments were evaluated on FMNIST and CIFAR-10 dataset. These datasets were randomly distributed among 5 clients. To reserve the Non-IID data, we distributed the images based on certain criterions.

Convolutional Neural Network with 3 convolutinal block following with 2 dense layers were applied. Convolutional layers were used as base layers and remaining layers as personalized layers. Number of epochs for each client differs based on the its computational power. Clients with better computational capabilities were trained longer than the others.

Results were evaulated by 4 criterions namely, accuracy, precision, recall and f1-score. Globally aggregated model were sent to each clients. These criterions were evalutead at each client's test set seperately. As a final evaluation, average of these values are used.

Obtained results showed that neither AHP nor FIS could made significant impact on FMNIST dataset. Though parameters of the models were different, the difference was not big enough to make impact on the decision making. But performance of the local models were increased in the CIFAR-10 dataset as shown in table 2.

Method	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Original	0.4125	0.4724	0.4125	0.4412
FIS	0.4325	0.5118	0.4188	0.4616
AHP	0.4325	0.5092	0.4188	0.4613

Table 2 Comparison of results in CIFAR-10 dataset

From the table 2, it can implied that average performance of local in all 4 crtierions were increased by 1-4%.

II. Conclusion and Future Works

In this work, we tried to modify the performance of FedPER algorithm using different client weighting apporaches which has been succesfully implemented to increase the performance of FedAVG algorithm. During the experiments it was observed that the applying these approaches to FedPER algorithm may increase the performance. But the improvement of the performance was small. These leaves room for further improvement. In future, other attributes which can impact decision making process could be added to both FIS and AHP. The rule set of FIS and preference matrix are also open to be modified. Different setting could make the performance even better.

References

1. Ahmed L., Ahmad K., Said N., Qolomany B., Qadir J., & Al-Fuqaha, A. (2020). Active learning based federated learning for waste and natural disaster image classification. *IEEE Access*, 8, 208518-208531.
2. Aliyev, S. (2023). Application of AHP for Weighting Clients in Federated Learning. *Azerbaijan Journal of High Performance Computing*, 6(2), 153-162.

**Süni intellekt: nəzəriyyədən prktikaya, beynəlxalq konfrans,
17-18 sentyabr 2024, Naxçıvan Azərbaycan**

3. Aliyev, S., & Ismayilova, N. (2023, October). FL2: Fuzzy Logic for Device Selection in Federated Learning. In 2023 IEEE 17th International Conference on Application of Information and Communication Technologies (AICT) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
 4. Arivazhagan, Manoj Ghuhan, Vinay Aggarwal, Aaditya Kumar Singh, and Sunav Choudhary. "Federated learning with personalization layers." arXiv preprint arXiv:1912.00818 (2019).
 5. Chai, Y., Jia, L., & Zhang, Z. (2009). Mamdani model based adaptive neural fuzzy inference system and its application. *International Journal of Computer and Information Engineering*, 3(3), 663-670.
 6. Chen, H. Y., & Chao, W. L. (2021). On bridging generic and personalized federated learning for image classification. arXiv preprint arXiv:2107.00778.
 7. Deng Yuyang, Mohammad Mahdi Kamani, and Mehrdad Mahdavi. "Adaptive personalized federated learning." arXiv preprint arXiv:2003.13461 (2020).
 8. Kairouz, P., McMahan, H. B., Avent, B., Bellet, A., Bennis, M., Bhagoji, A. N., ... & Zhao, S. (2021). Advances and open problems in federated learning. *Foundations and trends® in machine learning*, 14(1–2), 1-210.
 9. Qi, P., Chiaro, D., Guzzo, A., Ianni, M., Fortino, G., & Piccialli, F. (2023). Model aggregation techniques in federated learning: A comprehensive survey. *Future Generation Computer Systems*.
- Saaty, R. W. (1987). The analytic hierarchy process—what it is and how it is used. *Mathematical modelling*, 9(3-5), 161-176.